

INSTRUCTIONAL PROFICIENCY OF TEACHERS IN BUSINESS COURSES AMONG PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEIs): BASIS FOR INTERVENTION MEASURES

Rachel Ann Q. Capacite¹, Jeffrey G. Capacite² and Ma. Razelle Bathan¹

¹ College of Business Education, Technological Institute of the Philippines-QC, Cubao, Quezon City, Philippines

² Math and Physics Department, Technological Institute of the Philippines-Mla, Quiapo, Manila, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to explore the role of business education in preparing individuals with the necessary skills, knowledge, attitudes, and values essential for success in a dynamically changing business environment. Emphasizing the adaptability of business education to evolving technology and business practices, the research focuses specifically on the instructional proficiency of business teachers in selected Philippine higher education institutions (HEIs) and the challenges they encounter. The overarching goal is to propose effective intervention measures that can enhance instructional proficiency and address the identified challenges within the context of business education in these institutions. The study used a descriptive comparative to determine the differences between the three groups of respondents: the school managers, business teachers and students. Correlation is also utilized to examine relationships between different variables. In the context of the study, it may explore whether there is a correlation between teacher profiles and instructional proficiency. The respondents of the study comprised 8 (93%), school managers, 94 (10.98%) business teachers, and 754 (88.08%) business students, from selected HEIs and from the business administration program. The researchers opted for the use of ANOVA and Chi-square. Research findings indicate that business teachers have diverse industry and academic backgrounds, with high proficiency in various instructional areas. Significant differences in instructional proficiency are observed among private HEIs. However, no significant relationship is found between teacher profiles and instructional proficiency. Identified

challenges include limited industry support and networking opportunities. The study's findings have yielded several significant conclusions. Firstly, it is recommended to implement the proposed Teaching Capability Program, recognizing its potential to augment the instructional proficiency of business teachers. Secondly, the study affirms the exemplary instructional proficiency of business teachers, reflecting positively on the overall quality of business education. Notably, divergent assessments between school managers-students and teachers-students underscore varying perspectives on instructional proficiency, indicating a need for nuanced evaluations. To ensure the continual enhancement of business teachers' proficiency, a well-designed intervention measure has been proposed. This intervention plan is deemed suitable, acceptable, and feasible, recommending its practical adoption by educational institutions seeking to enhance the instructional capabilities of their faculty.

Keywords: *Instruction Proficiency, Business Teachers, Higher Education Institutions, Business Courses*

INTRODUCTION

Business education as the facet of educational training helps the individual to acquire relevant skills needed for living. As time changed, business education is considered to be an educational program that equips an individual with functional and suitable skills, knowledge, attitude, and value to enable students to operate in the environment they find themselves--as business arena continue to change.

Higher education institutions especially in the Philippines, have their role in the progress and development of society and aim to prepare scientific, technical, managerial, and administrative team in modern societies. From the use of typewriter to the computer, business curriculum has continually shaped itself to meet the needs of business—the gaps in technology and other important aspects in the business were addressed and adopted by the higher learning. However, the world of business become dynamic and the success and survival of business education constantly depends on its ability to adapt and keep pace with the needs of the recipients. Educational institutions have an important role in the improvement of a country's workforce. The teacher, as one of the most prominent figures in the academe, plays an important role in students' schooling and education. Business teachers are vital in helping institutions to deliver quality education through the effective and efficient utilization of classroom, subject business expertise, keep students engaged through appropriate use of teaching methodology and strategy; and conduct learning assessment and evaluation.

The researcher as a business teacher in HEI, delved in determining the competencies of the teachers handling business courses. The identification of instructional proficiency of business teachers lessens the industry gaps. There are some people in the industry that don't possess the right skills for the job available in the industry (FutureLearn, 2023). Market and employment gaps still exist as strengthened in the JP Morgan research and the speech of the newly labor secretary—discussed extensively in

the next chapter. As a result, the success and survival of business education constantly depends on its ability to adapt and keep pace with the needs of its recipient. These changes present challenges for both the learners and business instructors.

Accordingly, a gap in the market is an area that businesses don't currently serve but that there is a customer demand for. This could be a new service opens in new window that hasn't previously existed or a new way of delivering existing service—for students' clientele might or are still need to fill this gaps that business hasn't explored yet. It is believed that a dynamic business market needs transformational partners to fill this gap in whatever form. Therefore, it is vital that business education be a useful and essential component of transformation agenda if the curriculum of business programs across the regions is to continue to meet the needs of its students and the different industry that needs business graduates. Needless to say, that when schools are supportive of its human resources, it provides all the support to be able to meet the needs and address the industry gaps needs and graduate business skills. The primary principle of the competency model improves the performance of a teacher if they have all the competencies required to carry out their duties and responsibilities. Hence, specialization in a field and the frequency of performing a task will enable the teacher to perform the tasks effectively and efficient. With the different philosophies, ideals, and views on the skills gaps in business creating barriers between the stakeholders, this study was designed to explore the instructional proficiency of business teachers considering the mentioned factors. Also, would the credentials presented succeed in transforming economy through creative solutions that catalyze change in the field of business education.

Research Questions

The study explores the instructional proficiency of business teachers in selected Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and the challenges faced by them toward the proposed intervention measure.

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following:

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Specifically, this study aims to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of business teachers with:
 - 1.1 Industry Experience
 - 1.1.1 Previous industry experience;
 - 1.1.2 Length of industry experience;
 - 1.1.3 Job position in the industry;
 - 1.1.4 Bachelor's degree earned;
 - 1.1.5 Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.1.6 Years of teaching experience?
 - 1.2 Academic Experience:
 - 1.2.1 Bachelor's degree earned;
 - 1.2.2 Highest educational attainment;

- 1.2.3 Years of teaching experience?
 2. How do school managers, business teachers, and business students assess the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 Classroom Management;
 - 2.2 Student Engagement;
 - 2.3 Subject Matter Expertise;
 - 2.4 Teaching Methodology and Strategy; and
 - 2.5 Learning Assessment and Evaluation?
 3. Is there a significant difference in the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs as assessed by the three groups of respondents?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between business teachers' profiles and instructional proficiency in private HEIs?
 5. What are the challenges encountered by business teachers in private HEIs?
 6. Based on the findings, what intervention measure may be proposed?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive comparative and correlational research method to systematically investigate and analyze the instructional proficiency among business teachers in selected Philippine higher education institutions. This comprehensive approach involved describing the diverse profiles of business teachers, comparing instructional proficiency across various groups or categories, and exploring potential correlations between teacher profiles and proficiency levels. By employing this method, the study aimed to provide a nuanced understanding of the intricate relationships and patterns within the data, contributing valuable insights into the current state of business education and offering a foundation for targeted interventions and improvements.

Population and Sampling

The population of the study was people working and studying in private higher education institutions. The HEIs participants are the National University, Technological Institute of the Philippines, and Jose Rizal University. The sample size for the study was determined using purposive sampling. According to Crossman (2020), a purposive sample is a non-probability sample that selects a population's characteristics and the study's objective. A purposive sampling technique is used in selecting the school managers and business teachers in the business program. The business students were selected through purposive-random sampling. Taylor (2023) defined random sampling as selecting sample participants to derive conclusions and assumptions about an entire population.

Table 1
Population of the Study

HEI Participants	School Managers	Business Teachers	Students	Total
	N	N	N	
National University	2	35	3,034	3,071
T.I.P.	2	20	153	175
Jose Rizal University	4	39	1,900	1,943
TOTAL	8	94	5,087	5,189

Table 1 presents the population of the study namely: National University (3071), T.I.P. (175), and Jose Rizal University (1943), a total of 5189. The three groups of respondents comprised of school managers (8), 94 business teachers (94), and 754 business students (5087).

Respondents of the Study

As presented in Table 2, the respondents of the study comprised 8 (93%) school managers, 94 (10.98%) business teachers, and 754 (88.08%) business students from HEIs and from the business administration program.

Table 2
Respondents of the Study

Respondents	f	%
School Managers	8	0.93
Business Teachers	94	10.98
Students	754	88.08
TOTAL	856	100.00

Research Instrument

After perusing the literature, a draft survey questionnaire was submitted to the adviser, faculty, and experts for comments and suggestions. The revised questionnaire was then distributed to three groups of respondents to test run the questionnaire. The suggestions, corrections, and recommendations were collated and reflected in the drafted instrument for modification purposes. A questionnaire with three parts was formed to collect primary data. The first part of the questionnaire determines the profile of the business teachers with both industry and academic experiences. The second part measured instructional proficiency, and the third part determined the challenges encountered by business teachers in private higher education institutions. **Part I** focuses on the profile of the respondents in terms of the type of respondents and profile of Business teachers with industry and academic experience. **Part II** determines the instructional proficiency of teachers in Classroom Management, Student Engagement, Subject Matter Expertise, Teaching Methodology and Strategy, and Learning Assessment and Evaluation. **Part III** covers the challenges encountered by business teachers in private HEIs.

Validation of the Research Instrument

The survey questionnaire checklist was drafted several times before being forwarded to the research adviser and made the necessary correction. The experts in the field validated it. A dry run to co employees was also done to test the validity and reliability of the instrument. The study adopted content validity, indicating whether the test items represented the content the test was designed to measure. The pilot study assisted in determining the accuracy, clarity, and suitability of the instruments. It helped identify inadequate and ambiguous items such that those that failed to measure the variables were modified or disregarded completely, and new items were added. To ensure validity, the instruments used in the study were examined by the educational experts and adviser who are authorities in research.

Data Gathering Procedures

The following data-gathering procedures were observed:

1. The researcher sought permission from the school officials from the three higher education institutions to conduct the survey.
2. The researcher forwarded the online survey form via Google form to the Dean of the College of Business Education, and the latter then distributed the online survey form to the business teachers and students.
3. The researcher regularly monitors the responses of the respondents in the Google form to make sure that the required number of respondents in the study is met.
4. Talled the data by group. Forwarded to the adviser to check the data before it was subjected to statistical treatment.
5. Presented, analyzed, and interpreted the data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools for the interpretation of results according to sub-problems were used:

1. Percentage. This is used as descriptive statistics that describes a part of a whole. The formula that used in computing percentage in this is:
2. Weighted Mean. This is used to get the average frequency of the responses in each weighted item.
3. Ranking. This reinforces the percentage to show the proportional importance of an item considered.
4. Analysis of Variance. The ANOVA is more fitted in the research due to the comparison of more than two groups. This research has three different groups of small firms. The systematic factors have a statistical influence on the given data set, while the random factors do not, Kenton (2019).
5. Analysis of Variance (F-Test). It was used for unpaired small samples to reject or accept the hypothesis and to present significant differences in the responses of the respondents.
6. Chi-Square test. It is a statistical procedure for determining the difference between

observed and expected data. This test can also be used to determine whether it correlates to the categorical variables in our data. It helps to find out whether a difference between two categorical variables is due to chance or a relationship between them.

Likert's Scale. To determine the verbal description of the scale and range, the five-point Likert's Scale was used, and its interpretation follows:

On the Instructional Proficiency of Business Teachers

Scale	Numerical Value	Descriptive Value
5	4.20 – 5.00	Highly Competent (HC)
4	3.40 – 4.19	Competent (C)
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Competent (C)
2	1.80 – 2.59	Least Competent (LC)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Very Least Competent (VLC)

On the Challenges Encountered

Scale	Numerical Value	Descriptive Value
5	4.20 – 5.00	Highly Encountered (HE)
4	3.40 – 4.19	Encountered (E)
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Encountered (ME)
2	1.80 – 2.59	Least Encountered (LE)
1	1.00 – 1.79	Very Least Encountered (VLE)

RESULTS

Sub Problem No. 1. What is the business teachers' profile regarding industry experience and academic experience?

1.1 Profile of Business Teachers with Industry Experience

Table 3

Profile of the Business Teachers with Industry Experience

Previous Industry Connected	f	%
Banking	14	14.89
Business Process Outsourcing (BPO)	6	6.38
Construction	1	1.06
Education	6	6.38
Financial	4	4.26
Gaming	2	2.12
Insurance	4	4.26
Manufacturing	13	13.83
Real Estate	20	21.28
Retail Trading	24	25.53
TOTAL	94	100.00
Length of industry experience	f	%

20 - 24 years	10	10.64
15 - 19 years	21	22.34
10 - 14 years	30	31.91
5 - 9 years	25	26.59
Less than 5 years	8	8.51
TOTAL	94	100.00
Job Position in the Industry		
Admin Assistant	1	1.06
Assistant Manager	6	6.38
Team Leader	3	3.19
Managerial	56	59.57
Supervisory	10	10.64
Rank and File	18	19.15
TOTAL	94	100.00
Bachelor's degree earned		
	n	%
Accountancy	17	18.08
Banking & Finance	24	25.53
Commerce	8	8.51
Entrepreneurial Management	2	2.13
Financial & Management Accounting	1	1.06
Financial Management	10	10.64
Human Resource Mgt	3	3.19
Logistic Management	5	5.31
Marketing Management	24	25.53
TOTAL	94	100.00
Highest educational attainment		
		%
Doctorate	18	19.15
With Doctoral units	19	20.21
Master's Degree	56	59.57
With Master's units	1	1.06
TOTAL	94	100.00
Years of teaching experience		
		%
20 - 14 years	1	1.06
15 - 19 years	11	11.70
10 - 14 years	11	11.70
5 - 9 years	38	40.42
Less than 5 years	33	35.11
TOTAL	94	100.00

Table 3 presents the profile of Business Teachers with Industry Experience in terms of Previous industry experience, Length of industry experience, Job Position in the Industry, Bachelor's degree earned, Highest educational attainment, and Years of teaching experience. Findings of the descriptive statistics for the demographic characteristics revealed that the majority of Business Teachers were previously connected to Retail Trading (25.53%), Real Estate (21.28%), and Bank Industry (14.89%). Most of them had been in the industry for 10-14 years (31.91%), 5-9 years (26.59%), and 15-19 years (22.34%). Regarding Job Positions in the Industry, most

were in the Managerial position (59.57%), and some belonged to the Rank and File (19.15%). The Bachelor's Degree Earned by the Business Teachers graduated in Banking & Finance and Marketing Management (25.53%) and Accountancy (18.08%) graduates. More than half of the business teachers' Highest Educational Attainment got a Master's Degree (59.57) and Doctoral Units (20.21). It was also observed that Years of Teaching Experience 5-9 years (40.42%) and less than 5 years (35.11). Based on the result, Business teachers at the HEIs are qualified to teach business subjects as they graduated from business programs and were highly experienced prior to teaching. The result confirms that teachers in business education had industry experience prior to joining the academic institution. The result concurs with the statement by Nelson and Kahu (2017) that one of the areas where problems emerge is education and that experience is valued more than potential, and expectations and requirements often reflect this. In today's world, the educators are expected to have a great deal of professional and personal qualities, and extraordinary skills (Asio & De Dios, 2019).

1.2 Profile of Business Teachers with Academic Experience

Table 4
Profile of the Business Teachers with Academic Experience

Bachelor's Degree Earned	n	%
Accountancy	17	18.08
Banking and Finance	24	25.53
Commerce	8	8.51
Entrepreneurial Management	2	2.13
Financial & Management Accounting	11	11.70
Human Resource Management	3	3.19
Logistic Management	5	5.32
Marketing Management	24	25.53
TOTAL	94	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	f	%
Doctorate	18	19.15
With Doctoral units	19	20.21
Master's Degree	56	59.57
With Master's units	1	1.06
TOTAL	94	100.00
Years of Teaching Experience	n	%
20-24 years	1	1.06
15-19 years	11	11.70
10-14 years	11	11.70
5- 9 years	38	40.42
Less than 5 years	33	35.11
TOTAL	94	100.00

Table 4 revealed business teachers with Academic Experience in terms of Bachelor's degree earned, Highest educational attainment, and Years of teaching experience. Highest Educational Attainment of Business Teachers with academic

experience showed that more than half graduated Master's Degree (59.57%), teachers with Doctoral Units (20.21%), and graduated with a Doctorate (19.15%). Business teachers' Years of Teaching revealed 5-9 years (40.42%) and less than 5 years (35.11%). The result revealed that teachers with academic experience are more than qualified to teach business subjects, as reflected in their basic degree program, years of teaching experience, and highest educational attainment.

Sub Problem No. 2. How do school managers, teachers, and students assess the Instructional Proficiency of Business Teachers in terms of Classroom Management, Student Engagement, Subject Matter Expertise, Teaching Methodology and Strategies, and Learning Assessment and Evaluation?

Table 5
Assessment of Instructional Proficiency in Classroom Management

Indicators	School Manager		Teachers		Students		Composite Weighted Mean		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
Prepares for teaching with techniques ranging from counseling, focusing on understanding and mutually solving a problem, to behavior modification or ignoring inappropriate and reinforcing appropriate behavior.	4.88	HC	4.62	HC	4.48	A	4.66	HC	9
Prevents behavior problems through improved planning, organizing, and managing of classroom activities, better presentation of instructional material, and better teacher-student interaction, maximizing students' involvement and cooperation in learning.	4.63	HC	4.53	HC	4.50	A	4.55	HC	10
Emphasizes a positive classroom community with mutual respect between teacher and student.	5.00	HC	4.82	HC	4.60	A	4.81	HC	3
Adopts preventative techniques using praise and rewards to inform students about their behavior rather than to control student behavior.	4.88	HC	4.91	HC	4.45	HC	4.75	HC	7
Pronounces school rules, classroom rules, procedures, and consequences for positive outcomes.	4.88	HC	4.80	HC	4.49	HC	4.72	HC	8
Ensures a safe and supportive place to learn with clear routines and expectations	5.00	HC	4.77	HC	4.59	HC	4.79	HC	4
Encourages everyone to observe decorum and businesslike attitude in and outside the campus.	5.00	HC	4.90	HC	4.65	HC	4.85	HC	1
Uses affirmation teaching, which attempts to guide business students toward success by helping them see how their effort pay off in the classroom	5.00	HC	4.94	HC	4.57	HC	4.84	HC	2
Transforms a classroom into a community of well-behaved and self-directed business learners	5.00	HC	4.77	HC	4.56	HC	4.78	HC	5
Relates to students as individuals positively, treating them with respect, making lessons interesting and varied, encouraging, and telling them to believe in themselves and their abilities.	4.88	HC	4.83	HC	4.58	HC	4.76	HC	6
Overall weighted mean	4.92	HC	4.79	HC	4.55	HC	4.75	HC	

Legend:

Scale	Range	Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.20 - 5.00	Highly Competent	HC
4	3.40 - 4.19	Competent	C
3	2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Competent	MC
2	1.80 - 2.59	Need to be Developed	ND
1	1.00 - 1.79	Highly Need to be Developed	HND

As presented by the data, the school managers, teachers, and students generally

rated the indicators of instructional Proficiency of Business Teaches in terms of Classroom Management as “Highly Competent”: “Involves business students in the learning process by understanding the learning goal and the criteria for quality work, receiving and using descriptive feedback, and taking steps to adjust their performance” with a weighted mean of 4.85, as rank no. 1; “Business teachers are involved in the class to enhance the business learning experience of the students” with a weighted mean of 4.84, rank 2; “Develops and uses a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate learning” with a weighted mean of 4.81, as rank 3; “Prepares students for a career in business by familiarizing them with various business-related topics” with a weighted mean of 4.79, rank 4; “Uses assessment information to make decisions that support further learning and for opportunity identification” with a weighted mean of 4.78, rank 5; “Support learners in their immersion activities to feel the real world of work” with a weighted mean of 4.76, rank 6; “Integrates a pretest and post-test that effectively measure a learner’s relative competency within a core/business subject to *determine whether* learners satisfy the school’s requirements” with a weighted mean of 4.75, rank 7; “Involves students with different business-related organizations to deploy skills, subject knowledge, and also their relationship with the other students” with a weighted mean of 4.72, rank 8; “Learning and assessment are based on clear learning goals” with a weighted mean of 4.66, rank 9, and lastly, “Instruction and assessment are differentiated according to student learning needs” with a weighted mean of 4.55, rank 10, respectively. Hence, the obtained overall weighted mean of 4.75 is verbally interpreted as “Highly Competent.” It can deduce from the table that Business teachers observe decorum and businesslike attitude on and outside the campus. Furthermore, uses affirmation teaching as they attempt to guide business students toward success as their effort pays off in the classroom. The findings concur with Garcines (2018) found that regarding classroom management, respect for authority is in order, and a great deal of patience toward students is shown. As part of the routines, learning activities must start on time, so coming to class early and leaving on time are observed. The class periods are spent productively, so a particular subject’s objectives should be achieved. In case there is a disciplinary problem, it is handled effectively.

2.1 Student Engagement;

Table 6
Assessment of Student Engagement

Indicators	School Managers		Teachers		Students		Composite Weighted Mean		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
Encourage class participation for class presentation and discussion.	4.25	HC	4.28	HC	4.36	HC	4.30	HC	10
Integrates ways and teaching strategies to make the business course related student’s lives.	5.00	HC	4.65	HC	4.58	HC	4.74	HC	7
Start the discussion with icebreaker activities that help students relax and get comfortable sharing their thoughts	5.00	HC	4.65	HC	4.60	HC	4.75	HC	6
Encourages students to work on business cases or project that requires integrating ideas or information from previous sources.	4.88	HC	4.89	HC	4.58	HC	4.78	HC	2.5
Encourages business students to interact with classmates and instructors by making learning	5.00	HC	4.87	HC	4.61	HC	4.83	HC	1

collaborative and competitive.									
Engages business students to visually conceptualize their understanding of the unit under study.	4.88	HC	4.84	HC	4.57	HC	4.76	HC	4.5
Use small group discussions, debates, role-plays, or online forums.	5.00	HC	4.64	HC	4.55	HC	4.73	HC	8
Conducts individual consultations for the most effective learning modes to engage students, as they benefit substantially in both the learning and development process	4.63	HC	4.80	HC	4.43	HC	4.62	HC	9
In-class active teaching activities are included in the teaching category, such as applied activities, case studies, business videos, and interactive business lectures.	5.00	HC	4.79	HC	4.55	HC	4.78	HC	2.5
Encourages students' participation in peer-assisted study sessions, online practicing, and reviewing recorded lectures.	5.00	HC	4.70	HC	4.59	HC	4.76	HC	4.5
Overall weighted mean	4.86	HC	4.70	HC	4.54	HC	4.70	HC	

The assessment of respondents on the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of Student Engagement is in Table 6. As presented by the data, the school managers, teachers, and students generally rated the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of Student Engagement as “Highly Proficient” as follows: “Encourages business students to interact with classmates and instructors by making learning collaborative and competitive” with a weighted mean of 4.83, rank 1; both in rank 2.5, “Encourages students to work on business cases or project that requires integrating ideas or information from 4.78; rank 4.5 “Engages business to visually conceptualize what they understood from the specific units under study” and “Encourages students’ participation in peer-assisted study sessions, online practicing, and reviewing recorded lectures” with weighted mean of 4.76;rank 6 is “Start the discussion with icebreaker activities that help students relax and get comfortable sharing their thoughts.” with weighted mean of 4.75; rank 7, “integrates ways and teaching strategies to make the business course relevant to the students’ lives” with a weighted mean of 4.74; rank 8, “Business faculty provides optimal opportunities for students to keep their appointment with their college/university studies and thrive in an engaging and intellectually stimulating environment” with a weighted mean of 4.73; rank 9, “Conducts individual consultations for the most effective learning modes to engage students, as they benefit substantially in both the learning and development process” with a weighted mean of 4.62, and lastly, “Use small group discussions, debates, role-plays, or online forums” with a weighted mean of 4.30, respectively. These obtained mean values yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.70 and were verbally interpreted as “Highly Proficient.” It manifests that business teachers encourage their students to interact with classmates and instructors by making learning collaborative and competitive.

2.3 Subject Matter Expertise;

Table 7
Assessment of Subject Matter Expertise

Indicators	School Manager		Teachers		Students		Composite Weighted Mean		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
Able to explain subject matter clearly	5.00	HC	4.93	HC	4.62	HC	4.85	HC	1
Makes use of their subject knowledge to organize and use content knowledge more effectively for their students to understand	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.44	HC	4.77	HC	8
Recognizes students who are struggling and change the way the information is presented and discussed to make it more understandable	5.00	HC	4.93	HC	4.46	HC	4.80	HC	5
Provide students with tasks that are appropriate for their academic skill level and that they can easily accomplish in the allotted time.	4.88	HC	4.88	HC	4.52	HC	4.79	HC	6.5
Demonstrates problem-solving skills and includes critical and digital literacy.	5.00	HC	4.98	HC	4.52	HC	4.83	HC	2
Allows students to solve meaningful, real-life, complex problems	4.88	HC	4.52	HC	4.50	HC	4.63	HC	10
Reinforces essential concepts and helps students cross the knowing/learning gap.	4.88	HC	4.73	HC	4.55	HC	4.72	HC	9
Demonstrate expertise by addressing students' inquiries in a confident and knowledgeable manner.	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.57	HC	4.81	HC	3.5
Develops innovative spirit among students to make good use of available opportunities.	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.52	HC	4.79	HC	6.5
Allows learners to test their knowledge regularly, reinforces essential concepts, and helps them cross the knowing/learning gap	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.57	HC	4.81	HC	3.5
Overall weighted mean	4.92	HC	4.90	HC	4.53	HC	4.78	HC	

The assessment of respondents on the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of subject matter expertise is in Table 7. As demonstrated by the data, the school managers, teachers, and students generally assessed the indicators of the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of classroom management as Highly Competent, which “Allows learners to test their knowledge regularly to reinforce essential concepts” with a weighted mean of 4.85, rank 1; “Develop instructional strategies, selecting appropriate resources, and designing meaningful learning activities” with a weighted mean of 4.83, as rank 2; “Demonstrate expertise by addressing students' inquiries in a confident and knowledgeable manner.” and “Allows learners to test their knowledge regularly, reinforces essential concepts, and helps them cross the knowing/learning gap” with a mean of 4.81, as rank 3.5; “Break down difficult concepts into understandable components, use appropriate examples and analogies, and provide relevant context to enhance students' understanding” with a weighted mean of 4.80, as rank 5; “Provide students with tasks that are appropriate for their academic skill level and that they can easily accomplish in the allotted time” and “Develops innovative spirit among students to make good use of available opportunities” with a weighted mean of 4.79; “Makes use of their subject knowledge to organize and use content knowledge more effectively for their students to understand” with a weighted mean of 4.77, as rank 8; indicator 7 “Reinforces essential concepts and helps students cross the knowing/learning gap” with a weighted mean of 4.72, and lastly, 6 “Allows students to solve meaningful, real-life, complex problems” with a weighted mean of 4.63, respectively and yielded an

overall weighted mean of 4.78, verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. Based on the result, business teachers allow learners to test their knowledge regularly to reinforce an essential concept and demonstrate problem-solving skills and include critical and digital literacy. The results concur with the study by Del Mundo and Refozar (2013) that accounting teachers are qualified to handle subjects at the tertiary level. This result intensified accounting teachers' role in the academe, not only as CPA practitioners in their field but also in educational institutions. However, the problem identified in this study focused on students' behavior and attitude toward their studies. De Cree & Olsen (2023), clearly stated that teacher should be proficient in his or her subject and guide other professional and students on the project to ensure the content of their work is accurate.

2.4 Teaching Methodologies and Strategies

Table 8
Assessment of Teaching Methodology and Strategies

Indicators	School Manager		Teachers		Students		Composite Weighted Mean		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
Business teachers offer learners a competency-based approach to building their foundational business knowledge.	4.88	HC	4.91	HC	4.56	HC	4.78	HC	7.5
Business teachers communicate promptly and clearly to students, parents, and superiors about learners' progress.	4.88	HC	4.86	HC	4.48	HC	4.74	HC	9
Provides a venue for students to go beyond merely formulating a business plan.	4.88	HC	4.57	HC	4.45	HC	4.63	HC	10
Plan content instruction that will challenge individuality and entrepreneurial ability.	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.53	HC	4.80	HC	3
Considers national and local business environment in planning for instruction and strategy.	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.51	HC	4.79	HC	5.5
Uses various teaching methods, resources, and materials that allow students to be creative and innovative in learning applications.	4.88	HC	4.91	HC	4.58	HC	4.79	HC	5.5
Present business education foundational principles and develops entrepreneurial skills.	4.88	HC	4.93	HC	4.57	HC	4.79	HC	4
Enhances business problem-solving skills and analysis to develop decision-making.	4.88	HC	4.93	HC	4.54	HC	4.78	HC	7.5
Understand and operate in a climate that includes education and the business world as partners in career preparation	4.88	HC	4.98	A	4.56	HC	4.81	HC	1.5
Develop business students with valuable entrepreneurial skills and concepts for learning.	4.88	HC	4.93	A	4.62	HC	4.81	HC	1.5
Overall weighted mean	4.88	HC	4.89	A	4.54	HC	4.77	HC	

The assessment of respondents on the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of teaching methodologies and strategies is in Table 8. As asserted by the data, the school managers, teachers, and students generally assessed the indicators on the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of teaching methodologies and strategies as Highly Competent, "Understand and operate in a climate that includes education with a weighted mean of 4.63, respectively. Thus, yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.77, verbally interpreted as and the business world as partners in career preparation" and "Develop business students with valuable entrepreneurial skills and

concepts for learning” with a weighted mean of 4.81, as rank 1.5; “Plan content instruction that will challenge individuality and entrepreneurial ability” with a weighted mean of 4.80, as rank 3; three indicators “Considers national and local business environment in planning for instruction and strategy,” “Uses various teaching methods, resources, and materials that allow students to be creative and innovative in learning applications,” and “Present business education foundational principles and develops entrepreneurial skills” with a weighted mean of 4.79 as rank 5; “Business teachers offer learners a competency-based approach to building their foundational business knowledge” and “Enhances business problem-solving skills and analysis to develop decision-making” with a weighted mean of 4.78; “Business teachers communicate promptly and clearly to students, parents, and superiors about learners' progress” with a weighted mean of 4.74, as rank 9; and lastly, “Provides a venue for students to go beyond merely formulating a business plan” as Highly Competent. It can be deduced that teachers understand and operate in a climate that includes education and the business world as partners in career preparation and develop business students with valuable entrepreneurial skills and concepts for learning.

2.5 Learning Assessment and Evaluation

Table 9
Assessment as to Learning Assessment and Evaluation

Indicators	School Managers		Teachers		Students		Composite Weighted Mean		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
Learning and assessment are based on clear learning goals.	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.64	HC	4.83	HC	1
Instruction and assessment are differentiated according to student learning needs	4.88	HC	4.83	HC	4.48	HC	4.73	HC	10
Develops and uses a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate learning.	4.88	HC	4.98	HC	4.52	HC	4.79	HC	5.5
Integrates a pre-test and post-test that effectively measure a learner's relative competency within a core/business subject to determine whether learners satisfy the school's requirements.	4.88	HC	4.87	HC	4.50	HC	4.75	HC	9
Involves students with different business-related organizations to deploy skills, subject knowledge, and also their relationship with the other students	4.88	HC	4.83	HC	4.59	HC	4.77	HC	8
Prepares students for a career in business by familiarizing them with various business-related topics	4.88	HC	4.93	HC	4.57	HC	4.79	HC	5.5
Involves business students in the learning process by understanding the learning goal and the criteria for quality work, receiving and using descriptive feedback, and taking steps to adjust their performance.	4.88	HC	4.93	HC	4.61	HC	4.81	HC	2
Business teachers are involved in the class to enhance the business learning experience of the students.	4.88	HC	4.93	HC	4.58	HC	4.80	HC	3
Uses assessment information to make decisions that support further learning and for opportunity identification.	4.88	HC	4.93	HC	4.56	HC	4.79	HC	5.5
Support learners in their immersion activities to feel the real world of work.	4.88	HC	4.93	HC	4.55	HC	4.79	HC	5.5
Overall weighted mean	4.88	HC	4.91	HC	4.56	HC	4.78	HC	

The assessment of respondents on the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of learning assessment and evaluation is in Table 9. As stated by the data, the school managers, teachers, and students generally assessed the indicators on the instructional proficiency of business teachers in terms of learning assessment and evaluation as Highly Competent, “Learning and assessment are based on clear learning goals” with a weighted mean of 4.83, as rank 1; “Involves business students in the learning process by understanding the learning goal and the criteria for quality work, receiving and using descriptive feedback, and taking steps to adjust their performance” with a weighted mean of 4.81, as rank 2; “Business teachers are involved in the class to enhance the business learning experience of the students,” with a weighted mean of 4.80, as rank 3; meanwhile, “Develops and uses a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate learning.,” “Prepares students for a career in business by familiarizing them with various business-related topics,” “Uses assessment information to make decisions that support further learning and for opportunity identification,” and “Support learners in their immersion activities to feel the real world of work” with a weighted mean of 4.79, as rank 5.5; “Involves students with different business-related organizations to deploy skills, subject knowledge, and also their relationship with the other students” with a weighted mean of 4.77, as rank 8; “Integrates a pre-test and post-test that effectively measure a learner’s relative competency within a core/business subject to determine whether learners satisfy the school’s requirements” with a weighted mean of 4.75, as rank 9; and lastly, “Instruction and assessment are differentiated according to student learning needs” with a weighted mean of 4.73, respectively. Hence, yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.78, verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. The result shows that learning and assessment are based on clear learning goals. It also involves business students in the learning process by understanding the learning goal and the criteria for quality work, receiving and using descriptive feedback, and taking steps to adjust their performance. The findings are reinforced in the study by De Aquino et al (2020) that assessment and evaluation are related to both instructional objectives and classroom learning activities and are indispensable elements in the learning process. They are useful for gathering data/information needed for various interests. Among other techniques to do evaluation and assessment, The teachers can use tests to evaluate and assess, starting from the small one, incorporating evaluation into the class routine, setting up an easy and efficient record-keeping system, establishing an evaluation plan, and personalizing the evaluation plan.

Table 10
Summary of Assessment

Indicators	School Manager		Teachers		Students		Composite Weighted Mean		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
Classroom management	4.92	HC	4.79	HC	4.55	HC	4.75	HC	4
Student Engagement	4.86	HC	4.70	HC	4.54	HC	4.70	HC	5
Subject matter expertise	4.92	HC	4.90	HC	4.53	HC	4.78	HC	1.5
Teaching methodology and strategies	4.88	HC	4.89	HC	4.54	HC	4.77	HC	3
Learning assessment and evaluation	4.88	HC	4.91	HC	4.56	HC	4.78	HC	1.5
Overall weighted mean	4.89	HC	4.84	HC	4.54	HC	4.76	HC	

The summary of respondents’ assessment of the instructional proficiency of

business teachers is presented in Table 10. Looking at the data, the respondents generally assessed the indicators on the instructional proficiency of business teachers as Highly Competent, “Subject matter expertise” and “Learning assessment and evaluation” with a weighted mean of 4.78 as rank 1.5; “Teaching methodology and strategies,” with a weighted mean of 4.77; “Classroom management,” with a weighted mean of 4.75, as 4; and lastly, “Student engagement,” with a weighted mean of 4.70, as rank 5, respectively. Thus, this obtained weight yielded an overall weighted mean of 4.76 and was verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. It can manifest that business teachers can be described as prepared to teach, and students can rely upon their teachers as they possess Subject matter expertise, learning assessment, and evaluation. Higher education institutions abide by the policy provided for in CHED Memo Order No. 17. The result of the study is in consonance with CHED Memorandum Order No. 17, which specifies the core competencies expected of BS Business Administration graduates regardless of the type of HEI they graduate from. In recognition of the spirit of outcomes-based education. . . of the typology of HEIs, it also provides ample space for HEIs to innovate in the curriculum in line with the assessment of how best to achieve learning outcomes in their particular contexts and their respective missions.

Sub Problem No. 3. Is there a significant difference in the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs assessed by the three groups of respondents?

Table 11
Result of Significant Difference

Indicator	F-value	Decision	VI
1. Classroom Management	30.7068	Reject H _o	Significant
2. Student Engagement	4.7950	Reject H _o	Significant
3. Subject Matter Expertise	48.5600	Reject H _o	Significant
4. Teaching methodology and strategies	70.3043	Reject H _o	Significant
5. Learning Assessment and Evaluation	214.3888	Reject H _o	Significant
Overall	73.7510	Reject H _o	Significant

Degrees of Freedom = 2 and 27
Critical value at .05 = 3.487

The result of the significant differences among the assessment of the school managers, teachers, and student respondents in the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs is indicated in Table 11. As shown in the table, it could be observed in the results of significant differences obtained a computed F value of 30.7068, 4.7950, 48.5600, 70.3043, and 214.3888 were all exceed the critical value of 3.487. Hence, the overall computed F value of 73.7510 also greater than the critical with 2 and 27 degrees of freedom at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the statistical decision was to reject the null hypothesis and verbally interpreted it as significant. Since we failed to accept the null hypothesis, therefore, there is a significant difference on the assessment of the school managers, teachers, and students in the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. Thus, this shows that the school managers, teachers, and students do not concur with their assessment in the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter

expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. Since the result of the Analysis of Variance indicates significant differences, it is fair to investigate where the differences lie. Post-hoc pairwise means comparisons are commonly performed after significant differences when there are more than two groups.

Table 12

Result of Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparison for Classroom Management

Groups	Mean Difference	TK-test	Verbal Interpretation
School managers – Teachers	0.13	3.7333	Significant
School managers – students	0.37	10.9036	Significant
Teachers - Student	0.24	7.1703	Significant

Result of Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparison for Student Engagement

Groups	Mean Difference	TK-test	Verbal Interpretation
School managers – Teachers	0.16	1.7772	Not significant
School managers – students	0.32	4.3557	Significant
Teachers - Student	0.16	2.5778	Not significant

Result of Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparison for Subject Matter Expertise

Groups	Mean Difference	TK-test	Verbal Interpretation
School managers – Teachers	0.02	0.8665	Not significant
School managers – students	0.32	12.4796	Significant
Teachers - Student	0.37	11.6134	significant

Result of Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparison for Teaching Methodology and Strategies

Groups	Mean Difference	TK-test	Verbal Interpretation
School managers – Teachers	0.01	0.8690	Not significant
School managers – students	0.34	14.0689	Significant
Teachers - Student	0.35	14.9378	significant

Result of Post-Hoc Pairwise Comparison for Learning Assessment and Evaluation

Groups	Mean Difference	TK-test	Verbal Interpretation
School managers – Teachers	0.03	2.5489	Not significant
School managers – students	0.32	23.9900	Significant
Teachers - Student	0.35	26.5389	significant

Tukey-Kramer Pairwise Comparisons Critical Value (.05, 3, 30) = 3.487

It could be gleaned from the results of the Tukey-Kramer Pairwise mean comparison for Classroom Management, it shows that that there is a significant difference on the assessment between group school managers, teachers, and students. For student engagement, it shows significantly differ on the assessment between groups of school administrators and teachers. Hence, no significant differences between groups of school administrators – teachers, and teachers – students. Moreover, for Subject Matter Expertise, it manifest significant different between group of school administrators - students and teachers and students. Hence, no significant differences between groups of

school administrators – teachers. Furthermore, Teaching Methodology and Strategies, it asserted significant different between group of school administrators -students and teachers and students. Hence, no significant differences between groups of school administrators – teachers. Lastly, Learning Assessment and Evaluation, it demonstrated a significant different between group of school administrators -students and teachers and students. Hence, no significant differences between groups of school administrators – teachers.

Sub Problem No. 4. Is there a significant relation between the profile and instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs?

Table 13
Significant Relationship Between Bachelor’s Degree Earned and instructional proficiency

Indicators	Accountancy		Banking and Finance		Commerce		Entrepreneur Management		Financial and Management Accountancy		Financial Management		Human Resource Management		Logistics Management		Marketing Management		Total	χ^2
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E		
Classroom Management	4.90	4.84	4.82	4.84	4.79	4.78	4.70	4.79	4.80	4.76	4.68	4.67	4.43	4.49	4.66	4.78	4.76	4.57	42.54	0.0145
Student Engagement	4.76	4.76	4.83	4.76	4.65	4.71	4.75	4.71	4.60	4.68	4.53	4.60	4.40	4.41	4.66	4.70	4.66	4.50	41.84	0.0106
Subject Matter Expertise	4.96	5.00	4.93	5.00	4.95	4.94	4.85	4.95	5.00	4.92	4.83	4.83	4.57	4.63	4.94	4.93	4.90	4.72	43.93	0.0105
Teaching Methodology Strategies	4.93	4.93	4.96	4.93	4.88	4.87	4.95	4.87	4.80	4.84	4.81	4.75	4.64	4.57	4.92	4.86	4.38	4.65	43.27	0.0180
Learning Assessment and Evaluation	4.95	4.97	4.97	4.97	4.94	4.91	5.00	4.92	4.90	4.89	4.80	4.80	4.67	4.61	5.00	4.91	4.44	4.69	43.67	0.0173
Total	24.50	24.50	24.51	24.50	24.21	24.21	24.25	24.24	24.10	24.09	23.65	23.65	22.71	22.71	24.18	24.18	23.14	23.13	215.25	0.0709

Degrees of freedom = 32
Critical value at .05 = 43.77

The following table shows the results of the significant relationship between the profile and instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs. The result of the significant relationship between the Bachelor’s degree earned and Instructional Proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs is presented in Table 13. It could be gleaned from the data that the computed chi-square value of 0.0709 is less than the critical value of 43.77 at a 5 percent level of significance with degrees of freedom equal to 32. The statistical decision is to accept the null hypothesis of no relationship between the bachelor’s degree earned by the respondents and the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology, and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. This shows that the bachelor’s degree earned by the respondents is independent of the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation.

Table 14
Significant Relationship between Years of Teaching Experience and instructional proficiency

Indicators	20 - 24		15 - 19		10 - 14		5 - 9		Less than 5 years		Total	χ^2
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E		
Classroom Management	4.80	4.81	4.90	4.91	4.85	4.79	4.76	4.72	4.76	4.83	24.07	0.0021
Student Engagement	4.60	4.70	4.79	4.80	4.74	4.68	4.68	4.62	4.71	4.72	23.52	0.0037
Subject Matter Expertise	5.00	4.84	4.97	4.94	4.93	4.82	4.43	4.75	4.86	4.86	24.22	0.0298
Teaching Methodology Strategies	4.80	4.89	4.95	4.99	4.94	4.87	4.87	4.80	4.91	4.91	24.47	0.0040
Learning Assessment and Evaluation	4.90	4.85	4.99	4.95	4.53	4.83	4.91	4.76	4.87	4.87	24.25	0.0266
Total	24.10	24.09	24.60	24.59	23.99	23.99	23.65	23.65	24.19	24.19	120.53	0.0662

Degrees of Freedom = 26.30

Critical value at .05 = 26.30

The result of a significant relationship between years of teaching experience and instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs is presented in Table 14. It could be gleaned from the data the computed chi-square value of 0.0662 is less than the critical value of 26.30 at a 5 percent level of significance with degrees of freedom equal to 16. The statistical decision is to accept the null hypothesis of no relationship between the years of teaching experience of the respondents and the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. This shows that the years of teaching experience of the respondents are independent of the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. The result of the significant relationship between job position in the industry and instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs is presented in Table 15.

Table 15
Significant Relationship between job position in the industry and instructional proficiency

Indicators	Administrative Assistant		Assistance Manager		Managerial		Rank and File		Supervisory		Team Leader		Total	χ^2
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E		
Classroom Management	4.90	4.89	4.74	4.67	4.78	4.77	4.54	4.73	4.82	4.81	4.90	4.81	28.68	0.0104
Student Engagement	4.90	4.81	4.60	4.59	4.72	4.69	4.69	4.65	4.70	4.73	4.57	4.72	28.18	0.0072
Subject Matter Expertise	5.00	5.01	4.83	4.79	4.87	4.89	4.87	4.85	4.92	4.93	4.90	4.93	29.39	0.0007
Teaching Methodology Strategies	5.00	5.03	4.74	4.81	4.89	4.91	4.92	4.87	4.96	4.95	5.00	4.95	29.51	0.0023
Learning Assessment and Evaluation	5.00	5.06	4.77	4.83	4.92	4.93	4.97	4.89	4.99	4.97	5.00	4.97	29.65	0.0030
Total	24.80	24.80	23.68	23.69	24.18	24.19	23.99	23.99	24.39	24.39	24.37	24.38	145.41	0.0236

Degrees of freedom = 20

Critical value at .05 = 31.41

It could be gleaned from the data that the computed chi-square value of 0.0236 is less than the critical value of 31.41 at a 5 percent level of significance with degrees of freedom equal to 20. The statistical decision is to accept the null hypothesis of no relationship between the job position in the industry of the respondents and the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology, and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. This shows that the job position in the industry of the respondents is independent of the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation.

Table 16
Significant Relationship between length of service rendered in the industry and instructional proficiency

Indicators	20 - 24		15 - 19		10 - 14		5 - 9		Less than 5 years		Total	χ^2
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E		
Classroom Management	4.74	4.72	4.80	4.83	4.72	4.71	4.81	4.78	4.79	4.82	23.86	0.0006
Student Engagement	4.59	4.65	4.84	4.76	4.62	4.64	4.69	4.71	4.77	4.75	23.51	0.0025
Subject Matter Expertise	4.89	4.85	4.92	4.96	4.82	4.84	4.93	4.91	4.95	4.95	24.51	0.0007
Teaching Methodology Strategies	4.82	4.84	4.95	4.95	4.86	4.83	4.88	4.90	4.95	4.94	24.46	0.0011
Learning Assessment and Evaluation	4.92	4.89	4.99	5.00	4.88	4.88	4.92	4.94	4.99	4.99	24.70	0.0004
Total	23.96	23.95	24.50	24.50	23.90	43.90	24.23	24.24	24.45	24.45	121.04	0.0053

Degrees of Freedom = 16

Critical value at .05 = 26.30

The result of the significant relationship between the length of service rendered in the industry and the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs is presented in Table 16. It could be gleaned from the data in Table 16 that the computed chi-square value of 0.0053 is less than the critical value of 26.30 at a 5 percent level of significance with degrees of freedom equal to 16. The statistical decision is to accept the null hypothesis of no relationship between the length of service rendered in the industry of the respondents and the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. This shows that the length of service rendered in the industry of the respondents is independent of the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. The result of the significant relationship between the highest educational attainment and instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs is presented in Table 17. It could be gleaned from the data that the computed chi-square value of 0.0023 is less than the critical value of 21.03 at a 5 percent level of significance with degrees of freedom equal to 12. The statistical decision is to accept the null hypothesis of no relationship between the highest educational attainment of the respondents and the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management,

student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation.

Table 17
Significant Relationship Between Highest Educational Attainment and instructional proficiency

Indicators	Doctoral Degree		With Doctoral units		Master's Degree		With Masteral Units		Total	χ^2
	O	E	O	E	O	E	O	E		
Classroom Management	4.91	4.88	4.81	4.80	4.74	4.77	4.90	4.90	19.36	0.0004
Student Engagement	4.79	4.81	4.69	4.74	4.72	4.71	4.90	4.84	19.10	0.0012
Subject Matter Expertise	4.97	4.98	4.94	4.91	4.88	4.88	5.00	5.02	19.79	0.0002
Teaching Methodology Strategies	4.97	4.97	4.87	4.89	4.88	4.86	5.00	5.00	19.72	0.0000
Learning Assessment and Evaluation	4.99	4.99	4.96	4.92	4.88	4.89	5.00	5.03	19.83	0.0005
Total	24.63	24.63	24.27	24.26	24.10	24.11	24.80	24.79	97.80	0.0023

Degrees of Freedom = 12

Critical value at .05 = 21.03

This shows that the highest educational attainment of the respondents is independent of the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs in terms of classroom management, student engagement, subject matter expertise, teaching methodology and strategies, and learning assessment and evaluation. The findings support the study conducted by Francisco (2020) found a significant relative contribution of the teacher's academic qualification, teachers' content knowledge, teachers' instructional quality, teachers' evaluation procedure, and teachers' job satisfaction to the academic performance of the participants.

Table 18
Summary of Significant Relationship

Indicators	Critical value	Computed Chi-square	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
Bachelors degree earned vs instructional proficiency	43.77	0.0709	Accept H_o	No relationship
Years of teaching experience vs instructional proficiency	26.30	0.0662	Accept H_o	No relationship
Job position in the industry vs instructional proficiency	31.41	0.0236	Accept H_o	No relationship
Length of service rendered in the industry vs instructional proficiency	26.30	0.0053	Accept H_o	No relationship
Highest educational attainment vs instructional proficiency	21.03	0.0023	Accept H_o	No relationship

In summary, Between BS degree earned, Teaching Experience, Job Position in the Industry, Length of Service rendered in the industry, and Highest educational attainment vs. Instructional Proficiency vs. instructional proficiency resulted in a critical value (43.77, 26.30, 31.41, 26.30, and 21.03), degrees of freedom (32, 26.30, 20, 16, and 12), the computed chi-square (0.0709, 0.0662, 0.0236, 0.0053, 0.0053, and 0.0023) tested at .05.

Sub Problem No. 5. What are the challenges encountered by business teachers in HEIs?

Table 19
Assessment of the Challenges Encountered

Indicators	Business Teachers		School Managers		Composite Weighted Mean		Rank
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	
The formal education system lacks focus on developing creativity, innovation, and student mindset.	2.53	MiP	2.00	MiP	2.27	MiP	4
Lack of support in building relationships, networks, and social capital for teachers and students with entrepreneurial linings.	2.59	MiP	2.63	MoP	2.61	MoP	2
There is no funding support for students for start-up and procurement of products to help start the venture.	2.30	MiP	2.00	MiP	2.15	MiP	6
There is minimal support from the academe and industry to aid promising entrepreneurial undertaking to start and grow a business.	2.20	MiP	2.25	MiP	2.23	MiP	5
Availability of industry support for teacher's immersion	3.62	SP	3.50	SP	3.56	SP	1
There is no venue for students to go beyond merely formulating a business plan.	1.79	NAP	2.13	MiP	1.96	MiP	7
Lack of the knowledge to implement pedagogies prescribed in the syllabus.	1.53	NAP	1.75	NAP	1.64	NAP	9
Teachers lack the training to apply entrepreneurial pedagogies.	1.70	NAP	3.25	MoP	2.48	MiP	3
Faculty members lack the knowledge and skills to manage the business market's complexity and unpredictability.	1.34	NAP	1.88	MiP	1.61	NAP	10
The faculty lacks business skills and literacy.	1.14	NAP	1.75	NAP	1.45	NAP	11
The faculty lacks the management skills to improve planning, organizing, managing classroom activities, and better presentation of instructional materials.	1.59	NAP	1.75	NAP	1.67	NAP	8
Overall weighted mean	2.03	MiP	2.08	MiP	2.06	MiP	

Legend

Scale	Range	Interpretation
5	4.20 - 5.00	Very Serious Problem (VSP)
4	3.40 - 4.19	Serious Problem (SP)
3	2.60 - 3.39	Moderate Problem (MoP)
2	1.80 - 2.59	Minor Problem (MiP)
1	1.00 - 1.79	Not at all a problem (NAP)

The assessment of business teachers and school managers on the challenges encountered in the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs is stated in Table 19. As clearly indicated by the data, the business teachers and school managers generally assessed the indicators on the challenges encountered in the instructional proficiency of business teachers in private HEIs, “Availability of industry support for teacher's immersion” rated Encountered with a weighted mean of 3.56, as rank 1; “Lack of support in building relationships, networks, and social capital for teachers and students with entrepreneurial linings” rated Moderately Encountered with a weighted mean of 2.61 as rank 2; “Teachers lack the training to apply entrepreneurial pedagogies” rated Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 2.48, as rank 3; “The formal education system lacks focus on developing creativity, innovation, and student mindset” rated Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 2.27, as rank 4; “There is minimal support from the academe and industry to aid promising entrepreneurial undertaking to start and grow a business” rated Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 2.23, as rank 5; “There is no funding support for students for start-up and procurement of products to help start the venture” rated Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 2.15, as rank 6;

“There is no venue for students to go beyond merely formulating a business plan” rated Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 1.96, as rank 7; “The faculty lacks the management skills to improve planning, organizing, managing classroom activities, and better presentation of instructional materials” rated Very Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 1.67, as rank 8; “Lack of the knowledge to implement pedagogies prescribed in the syllabus” rated very Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 1.64, as rank 9; “Faculty members lack the knowledge and skills to manage the business market's complexity and unpredictability” rated Very Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 1.61, as rank 10; and lastly, “The faculty lacks business skills and literacy” rated Very Least Encountered with a weighted mean of 1.45, as rank 11, respectively. Thus, yielded an overall weighted mean of 2.06 and was verbally interpreted as Minor Problem. This means that schools should better equip the business teacher through immersion programs and the lack of support in building relationships, networks, and social capital for teachers and students with entrepreneurial linings. The result justifies the study by Ajisafe, Bolarinwa, and Edeh (2015) revealed the issues in Business Education as the inadequacies in the curriculum content of business education, non-relevance of the course content, poor implementation of the curriculum, time allocation, current issues and debates, qualification and quality of teachers, and facilities. It was mentioned by Ferguson (2022), it is important that teacher must juggle curriculum and lesson planning. In conclusion, business education remains the foundation of human resource development which provides knowledge, skills, attitudes, and understanding needed to perform in the business world as a producer or consumer of economic goods and services that business offers.

Sub Problem No. 6. Based on the findings, what Teaching Capability Program may be proposed?

An intervention measure was developed to address the issues faced in business education. The intervention covers the Key Areas, Objectives, Strategies & Activities, Time Frame, Person Involved, Fund, and Success Indicators.

Table 20
Matrix of the Teaching Capability Program

KEY RESULT AREA	OBJECTIVE	STRATEGY	ACTIVITIES	PERSON IN CHARGE	FUNDS / BUDGET	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Student Engagement	Identify students who needs activities	Establish a supportive and inclusive classroom culture	Use icebreakers or warm-up activities Flipped Classroom	Faculty	P10,000	1 School Year (August – May)	90% of the students in the class participated in the activity
	Individual consultations for optimizing student engagement in the learning and development process.	Engage students in a discussion about their preferred learning modes.	Create a timetable for faculty consultation Academic advising sessions Mentoring programs Use Online	Program Chair Faculty	P10,000		100% of the students in the class made for a scheduled faculty consultation

KEY RESULT AREA	OBJECTIVE	STRATEGY	ACTIVITIES	PERSON IN CHARGE	FUNDS / BUDGET	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS INDICATORS
			communication platforms				
	Utilization of small group discussions, debates, role-plays, or online forums.	Select topics that are relevant, thought-provoking, and meaningful to students' lives. Choose subjects that allow for multiple perspectives and encourage critical thinking.	Fishbowl Discussion Think-pair-share (TPS)	Faculty	P10,000		90% of the students in the class participated in the discussion and role playing
Classroom Management	Prevention of behavior problems through enhanced planning, organization, and management of classroom activities, improved presentation of instructional material, and optimized teacher-student interaction, maximizing students' involvement and cooperation in learning.	Encourage students to share any challenges or barriers they face in their learning journey. Discuss specific approaches, techniques, or resources that align with their preferred learning modes.	Discuss Challenges and Barriers Personalized Learning Strategies	Faculty	P20,000	1 School Year (August – May)	90% of the students have been prevented through classroom activities
	Preparation for teaching encompassing a range of techniques, including a counseling approach for problem understanding and mutual problem-solving, as well as behavior modification and the practice of ignoring inappropriate behavior while reinforcing appropriate	Encourage students to reflect on their own behavior, identify areas for improvement, and set goals for behavior modification. Acknowledge and reward students when they exhibit desired behaviors, such as active participation, respectful communication, or following instructions. Actively monitor	Monitor and observe Teach Self-Regulation Skills	Faculty	P20,000		Achieved 100% preparation of teaching techniques

KEY RESULT AREA	OBJECTIVE	STRATEGY	ACTIVITIES	PERSON IN CHARGE	FUNDS / BUDGET	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS INDICATORS
	behavior.	and observe students' behavior to identify instances of appropriate and inappropriate behavior.					
	Announcement and enforcement of school rules, classroom rules, procedures, and consequences to foster positive outcomes.	Organize the presentation of the rules, procedures, and consequences in a structured and logical manner. Explain the rationale behind each rule, procedure, or consequence. Demonstrate how to follow the rules, adhere to the procedures, and handle consequences calmly and respectfully.	Rule Presentation and Discussion Model Behavior Rule Collage	Faculty	P20,000		100% enforcement of school classroom rules and procedures
Teaching Methodology & Strategies	Provision of an avenue for students to extend their efforts beyond the formulation of a business plan.	Conduct or join a business idea competition	Business plan development	Faculty	P20,000	1 School Year (August – May)	Achieved 90% of students' formulation of business plan
	Timely and clear communication by business teachers to students, parents, and superiors regarding learners' progress.	Establish Communication Channels Prepare a progress report for individual learners	Student Progress Report	Faculty	P20,000		100% timely communication to parents and superiors regarding learners
	Enhancement of business problem-solving skills and analysis for the development of decision-making.	Utilized Problem-Based Learning	Give students a Real-World Case Studies Simulations and Role-Playing Exercises Group Projects and Collaboration	Faculty	P20,000		90% of business problem solving skills are enhanced
Subject Matter Expertise	Facilitation of student engagement	Assign activities involving	Internships or Work-Based Learning	VPAA Dean	P1,000,000	1 School Year	90% of the students in the class

KEY RESULT AREA	OBJECTIVE	STRATEGY	ACTIVITIES	PERSON IN CHARGE	FUNDS / BUDGET	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS INDICATORS
	in solving meaningful, real-life, complex problems.	relevant, meaningful, and real-life application	Cross-Curricular Projects Field Studies and Site Visits Authentic Assessments	Program Head Faculty		(August – May)	participate in cross-curricular projects, authentic assessments, field studies and site visits
	Reinforcement of essential concepts and assistance in bridging the knowing/learning gap for students.	Conduct activities involving unlocking difficulties such as defining terms and concepts, relation to other fields, identifying prior knowledge	Concept Mapping Conceptualize through Examples and Analogies	Faculty	P100,000		Conducted 100% on activities unlocking difficulties
	Utilization of subject knowledge to enhance the organization and effective utilization of content knowledge for student understanding	Design activities or exercises that gradually scaffold students' understanding	Scaffolded Activities	Faculty	P100,000		Utilized 100% of the subject knowledge
Learning Assessment & Evaluation	Differentiation of instruction and assessment based on student learning needs	Review the teaching, and learning activities to ensure that it is aligned with the assessment and learning objectives	Horizontal and Vertical Alignment of Learning Outcomes	Dean Program Chair Faculty	P1,000,000	1 School Year (August – May)	Instructional assessment based on student learning skills have been 100% differentiated
	Integration of a pre-test and post-test that effectively assesses a learner's relative competency within a core/business subject, aiming to determine whether learners meet the school's requirements.	Conduct mapping of pre-test and post-test given on core/business subjects if it measures learners' competency	Develop pre-test and post-test activity	Faculty	P100,000		100% integration of pre-test and post-test to assess learner's competency
	Engagement of students with various business-related organizations to apply skills,	Coordinate internships or work placements with the selected organizations.	Internships or Work-Based Learning Immersion Program	VPAA Dean Program Head	P1,000,000		100% of engagement of students on various business-related

KEY RESULT AREA	OBJECTIVE	STRATEGY	ACTIVITIES	PERSON IN CHARGE	FUNDS / BUDGET	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS INDICATORS
	subject knowledge, and foster relationships with other students.	Reach out to the identified organizations / industries and establish partnerships		Faculty			organization to apply skills

DISCUSSION

1. On the business teachers' profile with industry experience and academic experience

The business teachers with industry experience revealed that they were previously connected to Retail Trading (25.53%) and Real Estate as they had been in the industry for 10-14 years (31.91%) and mostly occupying Managerial positions (59.57%) with earned BS Banking & Finance and Marketing Management (25.53%) and Accountancy (18.08%) graduates. More than half of the business teachers with Master's Degrees (59.57%); and have been teaching for 5-9 years (40.42%). Meanwhile, for business teachers with Academic Experience: Highest Educational, more than half graduated Master's Degree (59.57%); Years of Teaching revealed 5-9 years (40.42%) and less than 5 years (35.11%); and graduated their baccalaureate program in Banking & Finance and Marketing Management (25.53%).

2. On the Instructional Proficiency of Business Teachers in Classroom Management, Student Engagement, Subject Matter Expertise, Teaching Methodology, and Strategies, and Learning Assessment and Evaluation

The instructional proficiency of business teachers in Subject Matter Expertise, Learning Assessment & Evaluation, Teaching methodologies & strategies, Classroom Management, and Student Engagement were rated as Highly Competent, with a grand mean of 4.76.

3. On the significant comparison

The computed F value of 57.6308 with 2 and 12 degrees of freedom is greater than the critical value of 3.89 at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the statistical decision was to reject the null hypothesis and verbally interpreted it as significant.

4. On the significant relationship between the profile and the instructional proficiency of business teachers

In summary, Between BS degree earned, Teaching Experience, Job Position in the Industry, Length of Service rendered in the industry, and Highest educational attainment vs. instructional proficiency resulted in a critical value (43.77, 26.30, 31.41, 26.30, and 21.03), degrees of freedom (32, 26.30, 20, 16, and 12), the computed chi-square (0.0709, 0.0662, 0.0236, 0.0053, 0.0053, and 0.0023) tested at .05. The statistical decision is to accept the null hypothesis of No Relationship between the profiles and the instructional proficiency of business teachers.

5. On the challenges encountered by business teachers in HEIs
The prevalent challenges faced by the business teachers of HEIs revealed that the availability of industry support for teacher immersion and the lack of support in building relationships, networks (Encountered), and social capital for teachers and students (Moderately Encountered) as supported by mean values of 3.56 and 2.61, respectively with an overall value of 2.06, described as Least Encountered.
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Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the conclusions were derived:

1. Adaptation of the proposed Teaching Capability Program.
2. Business teachers excel in their instructional proficiency.
3. The school managers-students and teachers-students do not share the same assessments.
4. Concerns met are found to be minimal.
5. The proposed intervention measure was developed to address the continuity and sustainability of teachers' proficiency.

Recommendations

1. Adapt the proposed Teaching Capability Program.
2. School managers may consider the strategies presented in the output of the study.
3. Conduct an immersion program for business teachers to keep them updated on the dynamics of the environment. This could be done by establishing strong partnerships with the industry for teachers' immersion programs.
4. The proposed output can be regularly subjected to review and improvement. Apply and retool it to other schools.
5. The issues slightly encountered should be addressed as follows:
 - 5.1. Availability of industry support for teacher's immersion. Establish partnerships or collaborations with various industries.
 - 5.2 Lack of support in building relationships, networks, and social capital for teachers and students with entrepreneurial linings. Create a platform or community where teachers and students with entrepreneurial interests can come together, share ideas, and collaborate. This could be an online forum, a social media group, or a dedicated physical space within the school.
 - 5.3 Teachers lack the training to apply entrepreneurial pedagogies. Organize workshops, seminars, or training sessions specifically focused on entrepreneurial pedagogies. These programs should provide teachers with an overview of entrepreneurship education, examples of best practices, and practical strategies for incorporating entrepreneurial elements into their teaching.
6. Further study may be conducted in different settings but similar variables to validate the result of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is a declaration by the author/s in his/their own words and in paragraph form which includes compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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